

To Develop and Evaluate A Tablet Formulation Containinng Cassia Alata Leaf Extract for Its Effectiveness in The Management of Helminthic Infections

Mayank Harne*¹, Jija Lode², Chitrlekha Therkar³

¹Department of Pharmaceutical Science, Siddhivinayak College of Pharmacy, Warora, 442914, Chandrapur, Maharashtra, India.

²Department of Pharmaceutical Science, Sai College of Pharmacy, Mangli -Tumsar,441912, Bhandara, Maharashtra, India.

³Department of Pharmaceutical Science, Prabhat Institute of Pharmacy, Rui- Bramhapuri 441206 Chandrapur, Maharashtra, India

ABSTRACT

Cassia alata, commonly referred to as "Ketepeng Cina" in Indonesia and "Gelenggang" in Malaysia, is a well-known plant in traditional medicine, especially for treating various ailments, primarily skin disorders. Cassia alata, a member of the Caesalpinaceae family, has been traditionally used in Indian folk medicine for its diverse pharmacological activities, including anthelmintic, antioxidant, antifungal, and anti-inflammatory, anticancer properties. Several bioactive compounds have been isolated from this plant, particularly from its leaves. These include alatinon, alanonal, various flavones, flavanols, flavonoid glycosides, and β -sitosterol-D-glucoside. While most phytochemicals have been extracted from the leaves, other parts of the plant—such as seeds, flowers, and bark—also exhibit notable antibacterial and antifungal properties and warrant further exploration. The therapeutic effects of Cassia alata are strongly associated with its diverse secondary metabolites, which contribute to its wide-ranging pharmacological actions.

Keywords: Cassia alata, Anthelmintic properties, Herbal medicine, Physicochemical constituent, Pharmacological activity

INTRODUCTION

Helminthic parasitic infections pose a significant challenge in livestock production systems, often reducing productivity and health in animals. The conventional strategy for controlling such infections largely relies on the use of anthelmintic drugs. However, the prolonged and widespread application of these drugs has led to the emergence of drug-resistant helminth strains, raising serious concerns about the sustainability of current treatment methods. Since only a limited number of effective compounds are available, careful use and strategic management are essential to prevent further resistance [1]. Helminthiasis, an infection caused by parasitic worms, has been recognized since ancient times and remains prevalent, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions. Anthelmintic agents are substances used to destroy or expel intestinal worms.

Those that eliminate parasites without killing them are called vermifuges, while those that kill them outright are known as vermicides. Historically, many early anthelmintics were derived from plant sources. Although many of these are now obsolete, *Aspidium* remains in occasional use. Notable developments in synthetic anthelmintics include the identification of isothiouonium salts with worm-killing properties, the introduction of mebendazole in 1971, and the synthesis of praziquantel by Seubert in 1975. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), around 1.5 billion people globally—approximately 24% of the world population—are affected by helminth infections. In India alone, about 258 million individuals are infected. Plants from the *Cassia* genus, especially abundant in India and particularly West Bengal, are known for various medicinal properties. *Cassia alata* has been traditionally valued for its antimicrobial, antifungal, purgative, anti-

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

inflammatory, analgesic, antitumor, and hypoglycemic effects [2]. Other species like *Cassia angustifolia* (known for its strong purgative action and its use in managing bowel movements) and *Cassia occidentalis* (used traditionally as a laxative, diuretic, and for treating fever, skin disorders, anemia, liver problems, and menstrual irregularities) have also been widely employed in traditional medicine. In Indian folk medicine, decoctions prepared from the leaves of *C. alata* and *C. angustifolia* are commonly used for treating gastrointestinal worm infestations. These leaves are frequently cited in medicinal plant databases for their relevance in managing intestinal parasitic diseases. Such infections are particularly widespread in developing countries, especially among children, where poor sanitation and hygiene are common (Chan, 1997). Additionally, concerns over the side effects of synthetic drugs have fueled a renewed interest in herbal alternatives, focusing on the therapeutic potential of plant-based remedies [3].

Plant Profile:

General Information: -

Scientific name - *Cassia alata*

Common name - Candle brush

Origin North America

Availability-Generally available in many areas within its hardness range.

Biological source: -It consists of fresh leaves of senna *alata* belongs to family Caesalpiniceae.

Organoleptic Properties: -

Colour: -Green

Odour: -Unpleasant

Taste: -Spicy

Description: -Height: -10-14 feet

Spread: -10-14

Crown uniformity: - irregular outline or silhouette

Crown shape: - Oval

Crown density: - Open

Growth rate: Fast

Fig No. 1: - *Cassia alata*

Texture: Coarse

Chemical Constituents: -The constituents present in *Cassia alata* are flavones, flavonols, flavonoids glycosides, alatinon, alanon and beta-sitosterol-beta-D-glucosides.

Uses: -

- Antibacterial Activity
- Antifungal Activity
- Antioxidant Effect
- Wound Healing Activity
- Anticancer Activity
- Anti-inflammatory Activity [4].

METHODS AND MATERIALS:

Extraction and isolation of phytoconstituents: -

- The whole leaves of plant were wash in water and air-dried under shade for period of two weeks after which they were ground to powder with mechanical grinder.
- 150g of powder were extracted by soxhlet apparatus using diethyl ether as solvent near about 6 hours for removing all the fatty oils unwanted sticky substances.
- Then same leaf of powder is taken in soxhlet by the chloroform as solvent to separate secondary metabolite.

- Then the above procedure was repeated with the help of alcoholic solvent as ethanol then final crude extract was recovered^[5].

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Preliminary phytochemical screening of the different crude drug/formulation using alcohol as solvents for the presence of various phytoconstituents was carried out using following methods^[5]. For phytochemical screening and further evaluation, the extraction of marketed and in-house formulation of Cassia alata Anthelmintics Gutika were carried out.

Phytochemical Screening:

- Test for Glycosides.
- Test for Alkaloids.
- Test for Flavonoids.
- Test for Tannins.
- Test for Phenolic.

PHYSICAL EVALUATION:

Determination of Total ash: Total ash method is used to measure the total amount of material remaining after incineration is called total ash. Determination of total Ash value is determined for

identity and purity of gutika. A high ash value is indicative of contamination, substitution, adulteration, presence of silica, rice husk or careless in preparing the drug^[6,7].

Formula: Percentage of total ash = $\frac{\text{Weight of ash} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample}}$

Thin Layer Chromatography:

Thin layer chromatography can be defined as a method of separation or identification of a mixture of components into individual components into individual components by using finely divided adsorbent solid (liquid) spread over a glass plate and liquid as a mobile phase. It is based on the principle of adsorption chromatography or partition chromatography or combination of both. TLC plate is prepared by using fur methods i.e. pouring, dipping, spraying & spreading^[5,11] After development of plates, they were air-dried and Rf. values were calculated. The Rf value (Retention Factor) was calculated as follows

$$R_f = \frac{\text{Distance traveled by the sample}}{\text{Distance traveled by the solvent}}$$

Table No. 1: TLC Table

1	Standard 1	Emodin
2	Standard 2	Rhein
3	Mobile Phase	Toluene: Ethyl acetate: Formic acid
4	Stationary Phase	Silica Gel

PHARMACEUTICAL PARAMETERS

1) Hardness:

Hardness the measure of the mechanical integrity of the gutika it is the force required to break the gutika in a specific plan. the gutika must have a specific strength and hardness to able the with stand mechanical shaking during manufacturing packaging and transport. Pfizer's tablet hardness tester was use to independently test the randomly chosen tablet^[8].

2) Friability test:

The friability is measured by the amount of weight loss following tumbling. friability test is conducted in

the Roche friability apparatus by taking 20 gutika. This is consisting of plastic drum that revolves at 25rpm dropping the gutika through 6 inches in a fibrillatory to undergo shock, which is then operated for 100 revolutions the gutika are reweighed. The gutika lose less than 1.0 percent than the ghutika weight are consider as acceptable^[8].

- Weight variation test
- The weight variation test perform with ghutika the desired amount of gutika in number are taken weight variation test is perform where there is any variation in gutika if its variation more than desired limit which is 5% should not cross. Weight 20 tablet and then its average weight is calculated.

3) Disintegration time:

The state in which no residue of the gutika remains on the remains on the screen of apparatus. This test will determine whether the gutika disintegrates within a specified time when it is placed in liquid medium under the control prescribed experimental condition. Disintegration weight of gutika=15min

4) Dissolution time:

The time required for the dissolve gutika in a sample solution is Dissolution time of gutika is 14min^[9,10].

Pharmacological In-Vitro Study:

The anthelmintic study was carried both Ethanolic Extract and Chloroform Extract were dissolved in

normal water containing diluted to get concentrations of 10,25,50 mg/ml. Albendazole (10 mg/ml) was used as the standard drug. All the drug and extract solutions were freshly prepared before starting the experiment. Three group, with one earth-worms each, were placed into 10ml of desired formulations as following: Vehicle (normal saline), Albendazole (10mg/ml), and one sets of three different groups were treated with extracts of respective concentrations. Observations were made for the time taken until the paralysis and death of individual worms. The paralysis was said to occur when the worms were not able to move even in normal saline. Death was concluded when the worms lost their mortality followed with fading away their body colors^[12].

Fig No.2: Ethanolic Extract (10mg/ml)

Fig No .3: Standard Albendazole (10mg/ml)

Fig No. 4: Ethanolic Extract (50mg/ml)

Fig No.5: Control Group

RESULT:

Table No.2: Organoleptic characteristics of Cassia alata leaflet.

Sr.No.	Test	Observations
1	Size	4.5 cm length and 8 mm width
2	Shape	Oval & longitudinal
3	Color	Green
4	Odour	Characteristics

Table No.3: Tablet evaluation

Sr.No.	Test	In -house tablet formulation	Marketed formulation
1.	Hardness Test (Pfizer tester)	15kg	10kg
2.	Friability Test	0.9%	0.5
3.	Weight Variation Test (80mg% deviation)	±9	±10
4.	Disintegration Test	35minutes	31minutes

Table No. 4: Pharmacological In-vitro study

Extract	Concentration (mg/ml)	Time required to Paralyze (min)	Time required to Death (min)
Control Group	---	---	---
Ethanollic Extract	10	50	56
	50	15	18
Chloroform Extract	10	48	29
	50	7	11
Albendazole Standard	10	6	10

Table No. 5: Preliminary evaluation of Crude Drug.

Sr. No	Experiments	Observations
1.	Ash Value	4% w/w
2.	LOD	0.40
3.	Extractive Value (%Ethanollic Extract.)	3gm
4.	Extractive Value (%Chloroform Extract.)	3gm

Fig No.6: TLC Plate**Table No. 6: TLC Table of Drug Extract**

Sr.no	Drug Extract	No. of spot	Rf values(in cm)
1.	Ether	1	0.95
2.	Chloroform	2	0.92
3.	Standard (Emodin)	3	0.93
4.	Ethanol	4	0.92
5.	Standard (Rhein)	5	0.92

CONCLUSION:

The present study focused on the formulation development and evaluation of Cassia alata leaf extracts for the effective management of helminthic

infections. The physicochemical parameters assessed were found to be within acceptable limits as outlined in the standards provided by the Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India (API). Among the different extracts tested, the ethanollic extract of Cassia alata

demonstrated the most potent anthelmintic activity, requiring less time to induce paralysis and death of the worms compared to the chloroform extract. Both extracts exhibited a concentration-dependent anthelmintic effect. Preliminary phytochemical screening revealed the presence of several bioactive constituents, including alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, and tannins, which are likely responsible for the observed activity. Based on the physicochemical, phytochemical, and pharmacological evaluations, it can be concluded that the prepared formulation exhibits promising anthelmintic potential. These findings support the traditional use of *Cassia alata* leaves in helminthic infections and may serve as a referential basis for future human clinical investigations.

REFERENCE

1. Kundu S, Roy S, Lyndem LM. Broad spectrum anthelmintic potential of *Cassia* plants. *Asian Pacific journal of tropical biomedicine*. 2014 May 1;4: S436-41.
2. Fatmawati S, Purnomo AS, Bakar MF. Chemical constituents, usage and pharmacological activity of *Cassia alata*. *Heliyon*. 2020 Jul 1;6(7).
3. Anbu J, Murali A, Sathiya R, Saraswathy GR, Azamthulla M. In Vitro Anthelmintic activity of leaf ethanolic extract of *Cassia alata* and *Typha angustifolia*. *SASTech-Technical Journal of RUAS*. 2015;14(2):41-4.
4. Ibrahim, D., & Osman, H. (1995). Antimicrobial activity of *Cassia alata* from Malaysia. *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 45(3), 151-156.
5. Khandelwal, K. (2008). *Practical pharmacognosy*. Pragati Books Pvt. Ltd
6. Lohar DR. Protocol for testing of ayurvedic, siddha and unani medicines. *Pharmacopoeial Laboratory for Indian Medicine, AYUSH. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare*.
7. Savarikar SS, Barbhind MM, Halde UK, Kulkarni AP. Pharmaceutical and analytical evaluation of triphalaguggulka tablets. *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrative Medicine*. 2011 Jan;2(1):21-28.
8. Fairchild HJ, Michel F. Pfizer tablet hardness tester. *Journal of pharmaceutical sciences*. 1961 Nov 1;50(11):966-9.
9. Dixit K, Puacla C, Shankhe N, Pawar A, Pillai L, Rokade P, Wagh S. Standardization of Herbal Gutika: Review Article. *Int J Res Publ Rev*. 2024 Apr;5(4):1174–1186.
10. Al-Gousous J, Langguth P. Oral solid dosage form disintegration testing—The forgotten test. *Journal of pharmaceutical sciences*. 2015 Sep 1;104(9):2664-75.
11. Gorthi KR, Aravind G. Quantitative analysis of acetaminophen in Nuromol tablets by high pressure liquid chromatography. *Indian J Res Pharm Biotechnology*. 2023;11(1):1.
12. Devade OA, Mehta SA, Lohare SB, Takawale R, Jadhav DY. Assessment of Anthelmintic Activity of *Pisum sativum*. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res*. 2022 Sep-Oct;76(1):7-12.

HOW TO CITE: Mayank Harne*, Jija Lode, Chitrallekha Therkar, To Develop and Evaluate A Tablet Formulation Containnng *Cassia Alata* Leaf Extract for Its Effectiveness in The Management of Helminthic Infections, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2025, 2 (8), 27-32. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16742272>